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Specific features of the development of Japan in the XI-XII centuries.

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In the middle of the 11th century, the autocratic rule of the imperial family began to strengthen. A characteristic feature of this period is the increase in the influence of the emperor (former) who accepted monasticism in worldly affairs. He was liberal with the emperor's entourage. For example, he also had his western part. Their social support was lower and middle-ranking officials of the capital who were dissatisfied with the monopoly of the Fujiwaras in high government positions.

The strengthening of the imperial power in these years is indicated by the fact that one-time taxes from public and private lands were collected for the benefit of the imperial palace, that is, for the construction and repair of the imperial palace, and the establishment of uniform weights and prices (1072).

In 1069, Emperor Gosanjio issued an order to abolish all syoen that appeared after 1045. Its difference from previous orders is that it has practical measures, that is, the syoens of temples and private properties are confiscated. Many emperors were on the throne at this time due to tensions between warring clans.

Ex-emperor Monk Toba, who came to the throne in 1129, was able to conduct a somewhat successful policy. He abandoned the fight with the Fujiwaras of his predecessors, and most interestingly, instead of losing them, he began to form new ones. The main goal of this was to collect syoen lands in his hands, and he succeeds in this. He became a large landowner who owned 500-600 shoen (the Fujiwara family had about 400 shoen).

But such a policy not only benefited the emperor, but also led to a sharp increase in private syoen estates. This strengthened the independent economic base of the feudal lords and further strengthened political disunity. In the second half of the 11th - 12th centuries, the main social unit of the ruling class was formed by "households" in which marriage and property relations played the main role, not kinship ties. Such households relied on private ownership of land and property, and property was inherited from generation to generation. But in the families of local feudal lords and peasants, male inheritance was not yet established.

After Toba's death, a power struggle began between the Taira, Fujiwara, and Minamota houses. In this war, in 1278-1279, Tyra temporarily won, and without changing the structure of the state, he tried to put his relatives in all positions and issued various laws that changed the life of the country. This turned all the nobles against Taira, and the war against him was led by Minamoto Yoritomo in 1180. Minomota wins the war in 1185.

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During the war, a bakufu military government was established in the eastern city of Kamakura and consisted of:

Samurai Office (1180)

Administrative office (1184)

Court Office (1184)

The House of Minomota was very successful in establishing an independent personal government. He designated Kamakura as the capital. Minamoto Yoritomo received the title of special shogun (1192) as a military leader. He created his own management and control apparatus. He appointed administrators to the state and syoen votchina lands, and military governors to the regions. As Yoritomo was a talented politician and a bright general, he led the samurai clans and united the country under his banner. He was able to control the officials by buying one and losing others, provided lands to bury their wives, and even controlled some of them through marriage ties.

He thus pursued an autocratic policy. The early shoguns were surrounded by lower-class officials descended from Kyoto aristocrats, and the eastern samurai were not brought close to power.

The bakufu is limited to the military-police powers of the military government. A large number of small and medium-sized feudal lords and estate owners in the country were not considered vassals of the shogun.

When the imperial government recognized the bakufu, the powerful vassals quickly rebelled. Under the pressure of the imperial court, the military authorities recalled their autonomous representatives. From the 12th century, the military authorities began to go beyond their duties, began to register land, and began to collect taxes.

In general, as a result of the Taika reform, the Japanese state system has changed from the classic Chinese model to a system more suitable for Japanese conditions. Along with the modernization of Chinese institutions, the erosion of communal and clan relations led to the disappearance of the original dual system.

The 10th-13th centuries are characterized by the growing strength of the military. From the 12th century, although the military commanders were subordinate to the nobles of the capital, a separate military authority was formed.

Early samurai military units did not have the conditions for independent existence. They were dependent on the feudal lords of the capital and the administrators in the region.

Since the 10th century, the hierarchical hierarchy of civil and military positions has been divided. On its upper floor, members of the imperial family, high-ranking nobles of the palace, a large monastery, and high-ranking military officials stood. He was followed by middle-class military and rural feudal lords. Below are the specific features of the hierarchy of feudal land ownership.

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First of all, civil and military feudal vassals received a certain part of the income in return for some service, not the land as a fief. This situation changed in the 15th century, when feudal lords in the provinces had full ownership of the land, and civil feudal lords in the capital did not fully rule.

Secondly, the hierarchical relations in this period were based on property, but in some cases military service was also taken into account.

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